

and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* were given 1-2 d access feeding on diseased plants collected at Cianjur. The test insects were transferred to healthy Cisadane seedlings for 1-d inoculation feeding immediately after acquisition feeding and after a 9-d incubation. Only BPH that had 9-d incubation transmitted the disease (see table). Transmission by BPH also was confirmed using artificially inoculated source plants,

Seedlings inoculated at 7 d developed stunting and pale-green to pale-yellow discoloration 6-14 d after inoculation. Later symptoms consisted of striping or mottling on the second and third leaves from the youngest, rusty spots on lower leaves, and narrowing and shortening of leaf blades. Drying started from the tips of leaves before chlorosis spread over a whole leaf. Additional N failed to retrieve infected plants.

Most infected plants died 19-75 d after inoculation. Tiller numbers in

Transmission of a virulent strain of GSV by BPH and GLH.^a

Source plant	Insect	Inoculation		Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (%)
		Insects/seedlings	Incubation period (d) after feeding on source		
Field collected	GLH (2d instar)	30/10	0	30	0
	BPH (2d instar)	30/10	0	30	0
	BPH (2d instar)	1/1	9	60	23.3
Greenhouse infected	BPH (2d instar)	30/10	9	40	7.5
Greenhouse infected	GLH (adult)	1/1	0	30	0
	GLH (adult)	1/1	9	30	0
	BPH (2d insty ^b)	10/1	9	9	22.2

^aInsects were allowed an acquisition access feeding of 1 or 2 d and then were given a 1-d inoculation access to 7-d-old seedlings after no or 9-d incubation period. ^bSeedlings inoculated at 30 d.

diseased plants were not significantly different from check until 30 d after inoculation. Plants that did not die produced numerous small tillers. Leaves with symptoms responded positively, but not consistently, to iodine.

Seedlings inoculated at 30 d exhibited uniform RTV-like orange-yellow discoloration on the third leaves at early

stages of infection. Neither stunting nor narrowing of leaves was conspicuous in 20 d after inoculation. However, later symptoms were not markedly different from those in 7-d-old seedlings.

These results show that the infectious agent is a virulent strain of GSV. A recent field survey found the strain occurring widely in Central Java. □

Insect management

Influence of carbofuran dose and time of application on control of rice water weevil (RWW)

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The RWW *Lissorhoptrus brevivirostris* affects 10-28% of the land planted to rice in Cuba, and it is the most difficult insect pest to control.

Different levels of carbofuran 5% G (0.6-1.9 kg ai/ha) were broadcast before sowing (test 1) and 25 d after germination (DAG) (test 2).

Three plants of variety J-104 were sown in 12-cm-diameter clay pots. In test 1, they were inoculated with 20 RWW adults/pot 20 DAG. In test 2, 20 first-instar larvae/pot were inoculated the day after insecticide application.

All levels of carbofuran controlled RWW adults and larvae. Control was

Effect of different levels of carbofuran 5% G on RWW.^a Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba.

Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Adult mortality (%)		Larvae mortality (%) 10 DAI
	2 DAI	14 DAI	
0.6	72	82	98
0.8	70	88	98
0.9	68	84	98
1.1	68	86	96
1.5	70	88	100
1.9	74	88	100
Check	2	2	0

^aAv of 4 replications. DAI = days after inoculation.

greater when carbofuran was applied 25 DAG than when it was broadcast before sowing (see table).

In the field, the insect shows similar behavior in respect to the time of invasion.

Application must be done when larvae are leaving the leaf sheath after hatching; that is the stage most susceptible to insecticides. □

Effect of neem seed bitters (NSB) on green leafhopper (GLH) survival and rice tungro virus (RTV) transmission

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A reduction in phloem feeding by GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, the vector of RTV disease, is observed in plants with foliar or systemic application of NSB. RTV is phloem-specific. We evaluated RTV transmission efficiency of GLH feeding on NSB-treated plants.

Two-week-old TN1 seedlings were treated by 24-h root immersion or sprayed with 2,500 ppm NSB. Untreated seedlings were used as check. Each seedling was placed in a 15- × 1.5-cm test tube covered with nylon mesh and arranged by treatment.

Newly emerged GLH females reared on virus-free TN1 plants were allowed a 3-d acquisition feeding on source plants. One viruliferous GLH was transferred to each tube. One day after infestation